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“Uses of English for commodification in the
Semiotic Landscapes of Mannheim and Leipzig,
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Abstract

Commercial signage in public urban spaces is a site of language commodification, as businesses use language(s) to sell goods and experiences to their desired customer base. This study investigates the use of English in the semiotic landscapes of the German cities Mannheim and Leipzig, focusing on the symbolic value of English, as one specific kind of commodification, in commercial contexts.

Our analysis is based on a corpus of approximately 5000 photographs of visible instances of writing in any language from Mannheim and Leipzig, collected between 2019 and 2021 as part of a larger research project. Drawing on selected images featuring a commodified use of English, our analysis combines geosemiotics (Scollon & Scollon, 2003) and Ethnographic Linguistic Landscape Analysis (ELLA; Blommaert, 2013) with the concept of scaling (Stroud & Mpendukana, 2009) to examine semiotic resources such as spatial placement and visual design. In addition, we employ Membership Categorization Analysis (Schegloff, 2007) to investigate how signs construct potential customer identities, with particular attention to class-based distinctions understood through Bourdieu’s (e.g., 1977) notion of symbolic capital.

While previous research has shown that English in Germany is commonly associated with internationality and modernity, our findings suggest that in addition, businesses draw not only on global connotations of English, but also its local meanings to construct membership categories linked to age, lifestyle, and class, evoking luxury and prestige. Commodified English thereby becomes a way of communicating what is desirable that relies on all of the specifically local connotations of English as a global language and an anticipation of the audience for each sign, including their desires.

Keywords

commodification, semiotic landscape, English, symbolic capital, Germany

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Introduction

As we walk down a commercial street in any city in the world, we don't just hear language, we also see it: on billboards, in storefronts, on shop signs. In those kinds of contexts, businesses use language strategically to draw in potential customers: to tell us who their restaurants and beauty salons and hotels are meant to appeal to, and how buying what they are offering might just make us look and feel. In looking around while walking through such a commercial street, we are of course superficially aware (as savvy inhabitants of our world) that the businesses we are seeing want to sell us various products and experiences. What we may be less aware of, however, is precisely how they exploit the social connotations of different kinds of language use to do this. This paper concerns itself with this kind of *commodified* language use, in a study of the use of the English language in the *semiotic landscapes* (or SL) of the two German cities of Mannheim and Leipzig. The analysis of semiotic landscapes (originally conceptualized as *linguistic landscape analysis*) emerged within sociolinguistics to examine written language use in public spaces, and was defined as involving "the language of public road signs, advertising billboards, street names, place names, commercial shop signs, and public signs on government buildings" (Landry & Bourhis, 1997: 25). Because our interest here is in commodification, we will focus on the ways English is used in specifically commercial signage, such as the types found on the commercial street we were just imagining.

The mere fact that English tends to be ubiquitous on commercial signs in Germany would hardly be a surprise to anyone who has spent time in the country. Indeed, as Androutsopoulos and Chowchung (2021: 218) note: "English in Germany carries a high symbolic value, and its choice does not presuppose an international audience." This indicates that the use of English on commercial signs is not simply a superficial matter of shops wanting to communicate with tourists who might not necessarily speak German, but that it is common even when German commercial establishments are communicating mainly (or even exclusively) with potential German customers. Probing a bit further into the specific nature of that symbolic value of English, previous work on German semiotic landscapes (e.g., Papien, 2012; 2015; Takhtarova et al., 2015; Ben-Rafael & Ben-Rafael, 2016; Fuller, 2019) has found the use of English on commercial signs to be associated primarily with ideas of internationality and modernity. Again, however, given the widespread understanding of English as a global language not just in Germany but throughout the world (Park & Wee, 2021), the mere existence of these types of connotations is hardly surprising. What we are concerned with in this paper, then, is a more in-depth look at *how* and *why* English carries the connotations that it has on German commercial signs, and which social groups of viewers commercial establishments are trying to target through its use. What are the specific *functions* of English on a given commercial sign, in other words, and precisely how is English used to communicate with the people it is intended to appeal to? What is the function of English beyond internationality and modernity?

By combining qualitative tools for the analysis of the semiotic landscape such as *geosemiotics* (Scollon & Scollon, 2003), Blommaert's (2013) *Ethnographic Linguistic Landscape Analysis (ELLA)*, and Stroud & Mpendukana's *rescaling* (2009) with the tool of *membership categorization* (Sacks, 1992; Schegloff, 2007a, 2007b), which was originally conceived to analyze face-to-face interaction, this paper analyzes some

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ways that English is used in commercial signage in German cities to convey symbolic capital. In combining these methodological tools, we are able to analyze the semiotics of each commercial sign in our data (using geosemiotics and ELLA), the ways in which each sign’s semiotics relates to how the symbolic meanings of English are realized in a local context where it is not traditionally spoken as a first language (using rescaling), and show how potential identities are constructed for would-be customers on the signs (using membership categorization). We argue that the connection between English and different senses of *value* is more complex than the link to ideologies of internationality and modernity found in previous research, as we also find that it indexes aspects like cultural capital, luxury, status and prestige, escape and mobility. More importantly, we also find that the use of English relates to not just one age or social class identity group but a whole spectrum of them. The detailed results revealed through our analysis will help us understand the complexity of how and why English is commodified in places such as Germany where it is not traditionally spoken as a first language and where English does not have a colonial history, thereby shedding further light on how we might best conceive of the role of English in our globalized world.

Framework: Language commodification and membership categorization

Noting the change in the relationship between politics, language, and the economy that was spurred on by neoliberalism, Bruzoz (2023) traces the roots of language commodification to the 1980s, as resulting from the emergent idea that language itself could be transformed into a commodity. While investigating the commodification of discourse for changes related to the effects of capitalism, Fairclough (1992) focused on the colonization of institutional orders of discourse in which language was seen as a skill that could be marketed (see Bruzos 2023: 151). This led Chouliaraki and Fairclough (1999) to define the commodification of language as language that is “subject to economically motivated processes of intervention and design” (83, see Bruzoz, 2023: 152), a line of inquiry that has been taken up by scholars across different fields, such as sociolinguistics, discourse analysis, and anthropology (e.g., Heller 2003, 2010; Tan & Rubdy, 2008; and Park & Wee, 2021). Since many of these scholars focus on the (re) adaptation of English in formerly colonized countries, we frame the commodification of English in Germany differently. That is, we do so not in terms of postcolonialism but rather with attention to British and American influence during the period following Germany’s post-World War II occupation and reconstruction, as well as the later shift toward viewing language as a commodity.

We are aware that commodified English may have different value in Germany compared to other areas of the world. According to Graeber (2001), there are three streams of thought regarding value, or (in our understanding) value categories, through which English may become a valuable asset for those who can use it. One of these categories involves value in the sociological sense which involves conceiving of knowing and English use as “good,” “proper,” and “desirable.” This leads to Graeber’s second value category: economic value. Due to the desirability of learning English for a large group of speakers,

English is conceived as able to facilitate economic gains for those language users. Finally, given how widespread the language has become and the semiotic resources it possesses, using English also possesses a linguistic value conveying meaningful difference (Park and Wee, 2012: 25-26). Thus, individually and when combined, these values transform English into a commodity: with symbolic value becoming the foundation of economic value and subsequent generation of capital. As Heller (2010) explains, Bourdieu (1977; 1982) makes several arguments concerning the various ways in which language forms symbolic capital, a form of capital that may be used in markets interchangeably with material forms of capital. This means that the language a person uses may determine their worth in careers, relationships, or educational settings which in turn may grant access to new connections and opportunities to earn financial gain. Therefore, when we can imagine a space where language and linguistic resources underpin the exchange of symbolic and material forms—what Bourdieu refers to as linguistic markets—we are able to theorize how the sociological and linguistic values of English are able to form symbolic capital that can be converted into economic capital, a process Heller and Duchêne (2012) have linked to the discursive practice present in late capitalism.

This symbolic value, and the potential financial capital, depends on the values placed on certain practices by the users of a language, connected to what Bourdieu (1990) refers to as *habitus*. In addition, the commodified use of English varies and produces different effects across the globe. As Blommaert explains:

Long quote, this should be indented the world is not a uniform space and that consequently, globalization processes need to be understood against the background of the world system. This world system, as Immanuel Wallerstein has extensively argued, is a system built on inequality, in particular, asymmetric divisions of labor between ‘core regions’ and ‘peripheries’, with ‘semi-peripheries’ in between . . . Thus, the system is marked by both the existence of separate spaces (e.g., states) and deep interconnectedness of the different spaces, often, precisely, through the existence of world-wide elites (Blommaert 2003: 612).

This implies that when analyzing language commodification, it is just as important to focus on the location of the language use as it is to focus on the language being commodified, since interpreting the use of a language depends on whether a particular geographic place is interpreted as core, semi-periphery, or periphery for that language.

Globalization has created a prominent market for English globally and locally, as it plays a central role in facilitating communication and cooperation across borders and within local multicultural communities. Park and Wee (2021) explain that English’s role in globalization is partially a result of its global prominence during the colonial era and how language has been reimagined via globalization as an economic resource to facilitate global exchanges. This then has an effect on local markets around the world, where English is locally adapted, without necessarily losing its global values, e.g. as “an indicator of the important role the language [English] plays in a society and hence the high placement on vertical scale of prestige” (Lanza & Woldermarian, 2014: 499, see also Bohuslavská & Ciprianová, 2024: 59), something that Bohuslavská and Ciprianová claim is both fashionable and appealing to foreigners and younger English-speaking locals of a location (*ibid.*: 57). Moreover,

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English has come to be seen as devoid of its connection with a certain geographical place, and is therefore not perceived as a threat to local languages and cultures. In turn, this allows it to be accepted for use in and adapted to new spaces.

In order for us to investigate that adaptation and place the relationship of glocalized (i.e., the blend of global elements in a local context) elements of English within Germany (for more on glocalization, see Roudometof, 2016), we also need to examine the (re) adjustment of English from its global function to a local context. Stroud and Mpendukana (2009), in their study of multilingual signs in South African SLs, suggest a model to do so through the use of rescaling, differentiating between sites of luxury and sites of necessity. Rescaling is, “[t]he processes whereby persons, goods, cultural artifacts, imaginations, and languages are circulated and transported between locales and sites of different dignity” (Stroud & Mpendukana, 2009: 367-368), as the local actor appropriates a global resource and generates local meaning (Blommaert, 2005; Stroud & Mpendukana, 2009). Similar to recontextualization, rescaling goes beyond simply repurposing or redefining an element in a new setting, and adds the hierarchies and economic values attributed to a ‘foreign’ language placed in a new context (ibid: 368). Thus, scaling signs of luxury allows for aspects of symbolic meaning to travel and become embedded in local economies and, in turn, allowing for their financial commodification. This differs from signs of necessity, which Stroud and Mpendukana refer to as sites of more task-orientated communication, necessity products, and services (e.g., gasoline, food, firewood for heating) (ibid: 373). This type of sign is usually produced locally and manually with relatively little economic investment, resulting in materials that do not weather well long term. This approach of rescaling allows us to delineate between sites of luxury and necessity in the German SL to see what linguistic tools are being deployed to exploit the ideologies associated with globalized English in this specific local context. One focus will be its reference to class, an aspect rarely discussed in the LL/SL literature; a notable exception to this is Fuller (2019), whose mixed approach combined SL research with classroom interviews to study the language ideologies of English in Berlin and the impact on immigration and integration, arguing that while the connotations of English make it unique among the many languages present in Berlin—often associating it with eliteness—its use by mainstream and nonluxury businesses leads to a bleaching of its national, ethnic, and class associations (168).

The way in which we gain access to categories such as class and age in our analysis is through the concept of membership categorization (Sacks, 1992; Schegloff, 2007a, 2007b). In affinity to identity construction in interaction (e.g., Antaki & Widdicombe 1998), membership categorization theorizes the ways in which affiliation to particular kinds of people, that is groups, is done in interaction. Schegloff (2007b: 436) points out that these kinds of categorizations may be done through attributes that come to index a categorization. These attributes include category-bound activities, that is (mentioned) characteristics that are typically associated with a category (e.g., the characteristic of crying is associated with the category of ‘baby’). We argue that some attributes (e.g., use of language or other semiotic means) in our data link to membership categories of class and age. In particular, we argue that these categories are evoked to address viewers in the SL, in the sense that viewers may see themselves included in an evoked membership category. At the same time, the specific membership category is only indexed (e.g., through language and/or images) rather than directly mentioned, which keeps inclusion

open. In fact, a certain ambiguity, which includes indexing more than one membership category at the time, may serve to address a larger customer base. This use of membership categorization analysis also serves to provide some of the methodological tools necessary to guide us in our in-depth qualitative analysis of the indexicality of commodification in our data. This leads us to discuss our approaches to the analysis in the next section.

Method: Geosemiotics and ELLA as approach to analyzing the SL

The analysis of our data is based on the principles of *geosemiotics* as outlined by Scollon and Scollon (2003) which Blommaert (2013) expanded upon in his principles of *Ethnographic Linguistic Landscape Analysis* (or *ELLA*). Geosemiotics provides a framework for understanding the meaning systems by which language and other semiotic systems are located in the material world, while ELLA enables us to analyse the photographs that make up our data as something more than just captured moments in time; it allows us to analyse them as repositories of processes of genesis, development, and transformation that ensued before our photographer arrived and continue even after she has left the scene.

Scollon and Scollon's geosemiotics is made up of three separate but interconnected systems of social semiotics. The first of these is the *interaction order*, which involves "how we place our discourses in the world through a complex set of social performances" (Scollon & Scollon, 2003: 82). The second is *visual semiotics* consisting of both images and texts (Scollon & Scollon, 2003: 108), including aspects such as participants, modality, composition, and objects or artifacts (ibid.: 86). Finally, the third is *place semiotics*, which involves the 'emplacement' or geophysical location of a semiotic display within the material world (Scollon & Scollon, 2003: 166). They distinguish between three distinct semiotic practices: *decontextualised* practices (which consist of all the forms of signs, pictures, and texts that may appear in multiple contexts but always in the same form, such as brand logos), *transgressive* practices (which involve any sign that is in the 'wrong' place), and *situated* practices (which involve any aspect of the meaning that is predicated on the placement of the sign in the material world) (Scollon & Scollon 2003: 145–146).

Approaching our data from Scollon and Scollon's semiotic system of place semiotics allows us to distinguish between ways that an element of a semiotic display (such as a choice among languages, fonts, or images) can make meaning through *indexicality* on the one hand, a characteristic inherent to all signs, and *symbolization* on the other. As Scollon and Scollon (2003: 133) elaborate, "When a sign makes its meaning by its geophysical placement, its physical characteristics, or its placement together with another sign or object, we call that phenomenon indexicality. When a sign makes its meaning by representing something else which is not present or which is ideal or metaphorical, we call that process symbolization." Since commodification is a kind of symbolization, this aspect is especially relevant to our analysis.

Approaching our data from the perspective of Blommaert's (2013) ELLA allows us to make connections between the signs of the semiotic displays we analyse and the social expectations that are a part of their meanings. As Blommaert (2013: 29) points out, while

any photograph captured from the SL may seem on the surface to be a mere synchronous object, “this object is historically grounded and generated,” and needs to be understood in terms of the “normative-traditional complexes of social action” (Blommaert, 2013: 29), that is, the normative social expectations that shape each semiotic display and the socio-historical processes that produced those expectations, taking into account that different individuals may experience different kinds of looking⁵. Finally, our analysis includes ways in which local or “offline” phenomena need to be understood as “catching their dialectical interactions with the worlds of ‘online’ knowledge in which they are encased and through which they circulate and acquire their defining features” (Blommaert, 2016: 99).

Introducing our data and focus

For the purposes of this paper, we investigate the use of English in individual images of commercial signage taken from the German SL. We draw on SL data collected in two mid-sized cities in Germany, Mannheim in western Germany and Leipzig in eastern Germany, between 2019 and 2021⁶. This corpus of approximately 5000 photographs to date consists of all visible instances of writing in any language in predetermined smaller areas of each city. In both cities, these areas involved distinct neighbourhoods within the city centre with different sociocultural characteristics, which are also reflected in the SL. In Mannheim, this consisted of two areas: a portion of the southern part of the city centre close to (and culturally dominated by) the University of Mannheim, and a more working-class and immigrant-dominated northern part of the city centre. In Leipzig, this consisted of three somewhat smaller neighbourhoods that formed a similar overall geographical area: a portion of the central business district in the city centre, a portion of a more working-class area in the eastern part of the central city, and a portion of the area around the University of Leipzig library in the southwestern part of the central city. The choices to collect data in these areas primarily reflected the broader research questions of the wider project of which this paper forms a part, but also had the additional benefit of providing data from a cross-section of different kinds of neighbourhoods in the two cities.

In a first step of the analysis, we coded all photographs within the atlas.ti qualitative analysis software. These codes included what organisation or topic the sign referred to, what the communicative purpose was (e.g., a call to action, advertisement, argument, etc.), physical characteristics (such as materials, whether it was temporary or permanent, etc.), linguistic details (such as the languages used, register in German, spelling anomalies, and multimodal considerations), and whether distinct signs interacted with one another. For this paper, we focus on those photographs that were tagged as using English; this data base amounted to 2294 images. In a second step, we identified a narrow subset of 28 images of commercial signs that used English for commodification (instead of, for example, simply for communication). A more in-depth qualitative analysis of this subset then epitomised

⁵ See Collins and Slembrouck (2007: 337) who point out that ‘the relation between a sign form and its meaning can vary according to who is looking’.

⁶ This data collection is part of a larger project funded through the Canadian *Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council* (SSHRC # 435-2021-0528) entitled *Ideologies of English in the Linguistic Landscape* as well as a CFI/ORF Grant (# 37510) for the *Social Interaction Language and Culture Lab*.

different aspects of commodification. In the next section, we present five representative examples.

Analysis

First, we start with an example of *glocalized* English, that is, English serving in the simultaneous construction of the local and the global. This example also represents a creative but template-like use of English that relies on pre-existing and modified chunks from pop culture.

Figure 1. Glocalized English with American pop culture reference in Leipzig

Figure 1 shows a stand-up display in front of a German chain bakery branch in Leipzig. It is placed on the bakery’s terrace in front of chairs and tables where customers can sit. Bakeries that are also cafés are common in Germany. The display features an image of a loaf of bread sitting upright on a sofa. On the left side, white text within a dark blue square indicates the weight of a loaf of the advertised bread and its price in German. The bakery’s name is at the bottom, not in the shape of its usual logo, but instead using a font resembling the Netflix logo. The bakery itself was founded in 1945 in the western German town of Groß Sisbeck in Lower Saxony, but today has branches primarily in eastern Germany, specifically, in Berlin, Brandenburg, Saxony, Saxony-Anhalt, Thuringia, and a few in its state of origin in Lower Saxony.

Above the image of the bread on the sofa, “the Big Bread Theory” is written in English. This title, its font, logo, and text colour mirror the wording and design of a promotional TV show poster for the TV show *Big Bang Theory*, the word “bread” replacing “bang” in the original and likewise set apart with red colour from the other words in blue, and the bread loaf replacing the show’s character on the sofa. In the top right corner, small Instagram and Facebook logos reference the bakery’s social media presence. Between the title and the bread on the sofa, smaller text reads: “Egal was bei euch läuft, mit dem Heidebrot läuft’s besser” (‘No matter what’s going on with you, with Heidebrot it’s going better’⁷). “Heidebrot” is a local type of bread and the name translates to “heath bread.” The region where the bakery was founded is known for extensive heath landscapes. The word “Heidebrot” on the display is highlighted with a frame. In German, this constitutes another pun, as the verb for “going on” can also refer to current TV programming. Understanding the title pun requires knowledge of English, as the show is broadcast in Germany with its original English title and therefore could not have been easily replaced with a German equivalent. This in itself is noteworthy: While using English original titles is fairly commonplace today and has been for at least two to three decades, it is not a given and has, in fact, been different in the past.

This display is an example of glocalization: On the one hand, bread is such a quintessentially German cultural good that it earned a spot on the UNESCO list of intangible cultural heritage. Several memes⁸ about Germans and their bread exist, in particular complaining about the lack of bread while travelling abroad, as well as a show featuring an anthropomorphized loaf of bread (*Bernd das Brot*, in English *Bernd the Bread*). Bakeries like the one that placed this A-frame display are ubiquitous as separate stores or parts of supermarkets. On the other hand, the reference to an American TV show represents pop culture as a whole. Even though it is from the US, it is globally known, like much of American pop culture, which allows the bakery to draw on the linguistic capital (Bourdieu, 1977) of English and the recognizability of American pop culture to sell their local product. This process can also be described in terms of rescaling, thereby referencing the idea of a global American pop culture that is spatially distant but locally anchored through the display.

The use of the English language here is creative, but remains a modification of an existing title. It is a chunk lifted from pop culture context—and the recognizability

⁷ All translations by the authors

⁸ Such as this: <https://www.buzzfeed.de/assets/images/24/609/24609675-buzzfeed-de-QYPH.jpg>

of the reference is the point—rather than originating in its entirety by someone affiliated with the bakery. The next example (Figure 2) from Mannheim provides contrast to this reliance on a pre-existing title and the audience’s shared knowledge through its free use of English.

Figure 2. Free and original use of de-nationalized English in Mannheim

Figure 2 is a photo of another A-frame display in Mannheim. It is placed on a sidewalk so pedestrians may have to go around it to continue on their way. The display is located in front of an establishment called *Café XOXO Hugs & Kisses* to which it belongs. Aside from coffee, this commercial establishment offers bowls, vegetarian and vegan dishes. The name is not translated from German but is, in fact, in English. In contrast to the bread display from Figure 1, the display in Figure 2 is handwritten in white chalk, and all in English. At the top the word “Seed” is written and underlined. “Seed” is not the name of the place but probably refers to the name of a coffee brand. Below that word, mostly contrasting occasions and moods with question marks and “Coffee” with an exclamation mark as the answer to each of these are written: “Bad day? Coffee! Good day? Coffee! Stressed? Coffee! Happy? Coffee! Inspired? Coffee! COFFEE? Coffee!”. At the bottom,

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the text reads: “Order inside =) Thank you.” Despite being handwritten, the smiley is on its side, corresponding to a typed equal sign and closing bracket. In the top left and bottom right corner, little hearts have been drawn. The hearts and smiley, together with the handwriting, convey a more casual and friendly mood compared to the previous picture. In particular the smiley also references casual online culture, mimicking the restraints of drawing a smiley with a keyboard even though the person writing the sign was not under the same restraints.

Whereas the sign in Figure 1 represents a corporate production that may be specific to the country and the store but not necessarily to this particular branch, the display in Figure 2 is unique to this location. This is true whether it was copied exactly from somewhere else or not because it is handwritten in chalk, and thereby conveys a spontaneity in the production of the display regardless of whether it actually is spontaneous as opposed to a print production that may go through several planning stages. The sign is an example of a scaled sign of necessity that is produced manually with non-permanent materials (see section 2), thus indexing being low-key and hip rather than luxurious.

There is no German on this display in Figure 2, and English also dominates the rest of the space outside of this coffee shop. English is not decorative here, it is not a reference to a title, the words are not borrowed. Instead, this is the free and original use by the author. Moreover, it addresses customers directly at the bottom. The “order inside” is a directive, and, underlined by the handwritten nature of the sign, the author seems to be more directly communicating with the audience. The English use goes beyond language chunks or adaptation as in Figure 1. The standup display is focused on coffee culture, representative of contemporary Western coffee culture as constructed through pop culture. This is in contrast to, for example, Viennese coffee culture with its large coffee houses, which is also on the UNESCO list of intangible cultural heritage, and that has influenced coffee culture in European cities beyond Vienna or Austria. Viennese coffee houses served (and still serve) a similar function as modern coffee joints, namely as places for socializing and creative work, even sparking an entire genre (*Kaffeehausliteratur*, or coffee house literature). While the purpose and social behaviour in coffee houses seems remarkably similar to what can be observed in chain café branches or independent cafés—typically featuring outlets to plug in laptops—the modern version of coffee culture has evolved through American pop culture, and the use of English here creates a distance to Viennese coffee culture, aligning with contemporary international/American coffee culture instead and thereby creating a rescaling effect in which the distant coffee culture is brought into the local through placement and handwriting.

The use of English therefore does index internationality and modernity, but in the context of the store it goes beyond by constructing a particular membership category for their customers: The store serves food which is aligned with current, originally (but now internationally practiced) American-style healthy food trends, and the value of English here transcends mere modernity, overlapping with trendy food lifestyles that are overall either nutritionally healthy or, in the case of coffee culture, part of a self-care routine for busy people. This constructs membership categories related to age and class, as these coffee trends target in particular middle class people and students, whereas traditional cafés may carry a reputation of catering to people who are older or belong to the upper middle class.

The highly visible, public-facing use of English here sets this place apart from traditional places and identifies this establishment to the public not as anchored in local traditions but in sync with internationality and modernity. English thereby is deliberately used to advertise and sell the product and thus commodified. The customers are constructed as middle class people and students characterized as busy and cosmopolitan, not of any particular nationality.

Similarly to studies that draw a connection between the use of English and larger societal processes like immigration, we relate the commodification of English to processes such as gentrification in Berlin coffee culture (see Schneider, 2020) or luxury brands moving away from their local cultures and languages in advertisements. Moreover, this theoretical approach demonstrates how English in the SL reinforces notions associated with class (and age) by indexing cosmopolitanism, modernity, and privilege, allowing it to serve as a symbolic form of capital (Bourdieu, 1991 see Park & Wee, 2021: 72).

The following example features similarities and differences to both previous photos:

Figure 3. Decorative (emblematic) English, American identity in Mannheim

Figure 3 shows another photo from Mannheim, taken at a Five Guys branch, which is an American burger chain restaurant. At the time the photo was taken in 2021, there were 35 Five Guys branches in Germany, and with the exception of one in Brandenburg and four in Berlin (a city which is both—or neither—western and eastern, culturally), they are all located in western Germany. Ten alone are in North Rhine Westphalia, the most populous German state. We speculated whether the reason these branches are so noticeably clustered in western Germany might be a remnant of pre-reunification eastern and western alignments, or whether the very corporate design that prescribes this highly visible and visually dominant use of English was deemed more likely to succeed in western Germany, which has a longer history of normalizing English. While we cannot determine the exact reason, we find it noteworthy.

Part of the interior design is visible through the glass window in the photo. There are no images on the walls, only text, for example, “BEST ALL AMERICAN BURGER” and “FIVE GUYS KNOWS FRIES” written in capital letters about 1-2m in height. Upon entering this branch, you are immediately immersed in this very present but borderline nonsensical English. Of course, this text indexes American identity not just through the use of American English such as “fries” but also by specifically and explicitly referring to American burgers. While some Five Guys branches have their business hours written in German on the windows or additional offers and information on posters and standup-displays, this photo shows nothing but English and the corporate design that is not location-specific—despite the specifically American use of English. Five Guys branches across the world thereby represent a powerful rescaling effect as they become embassies or detached islands of commodified, distant American identity in which the local is erased (Irvine & Gal, 2000; Stroud & Mpendukana, 2009).

Like in Figure 2, the English use goes beyond individual chunks or the modification of pre-existing titles. In contrast to the previous Figure 2, the use of English is decorative or emblematic here, the pure informational content of the text is irrelevant: Customers are not looking for written information whether “Five Guys knows fries,” it is standard advertising language meant to persuade and convey moods and feelings rather than merely to inform. It is not a directive as in the previous photo, customers do not need to understand it, its main function is to create an “anglophone” atmosphere by covering the walls in English text. To some, this atmosphere would be relaxed and casual, to others potentially intimidating and foreign. For a fast food restaurant that typically may rely on a broad appeal, this serves to construct an additional membership category having to do with class: Namely, rather than being simple and down-to-earth, this “Englishness” may index some degree of cosmopolitanism associated with well-traveled or educated people. At the same time, it offers access to these membership categories via American burger culture beyond and more exotic than McDonald’s and Burger King—both well integrated in the German urban landscape for decades—at low costs. Like the display in Figure 1 (but in contrast to Figure 2’s handwritten sign), the design in Figure 3 is carefully planned and executed according to guidelines of corporate design, then distributed across branches without local adaptation because being non-local is the point.

In contrast to the explicit American identity indexed by English in Figure 3, Figure 4 shows an example of de-nationalized English in Leipzig.

Figure 4. De-nationalized English indexing luxury in Leipzig

On this A-frame display with a black and white design, the text at the top reads “Lakrids by Johan Bülow.” On the poster below, there are two containers filled with candy, one set black, one set white. Above the containers, smaller text reads “Danish Confectionary Lakrids by Bülow,” and at the bottom, “Crispy Creation Twisted Taste.” The flavours on the containers are also written in English: Crispy Caramel and Twisted Banana.

We were particularly intrigued by the function of “by” in the line “Danish Confectionary Lakrids by Bülow.” In a previous talk where we presented this example, we did an informal, casual exercise to explore its connotations: We blocked out the word “Lakrids,” the text above and below the containers, as well as the containers without blocking the swirls of the background, leaving as much of the layout uncovered, and asked our audience what they thought this ad was for. They listed products like perfume, make-up, and jewelry. When we asked them why, they said, the display looked and sounded like it was advertising luxury items. Apart from the sleek and elegant layout and design, possibly influenced by Scandinavian trends, this connotation of luxury is carried by “by,” necessarily in English. In products all over the world, it implies that something is designed, not merely produced, and therefore indexes luxury. Similarly, the elevated word choice “confectionary” helps elevate the brand and implies the involvement of a specialized chef, in contrast to mass-

produced, industrialized candy (even if Lakrids is, in fact, mass-produced). As in Figure 2, connotations of class are deliberately used: Luxury is equated with quality, reflected in price and exclusivity, both limiting accessibility. Luxury items offer a means of social positioning to consumers, to communicate belonging to a more affluent social class. To increase the appeal of a product, it may therefore be coded as “luxurious” by associating it with membership categories involving luxury. As discussed above, such devices may include layout and design elements and language choice.

In contrast to the previous photo in Figure 3, the use of English here does not index a particular nationality. It is, in fact, a Danish brand, and therefore not from a place typically thought of as primarily English-speaking. This provides an interesting contrast to the previous examples. Although the bakery display in Figure 1 also conveys aspects of globality, it does so by maintaining the duality of glocalization, connecting the global with anchoring local references that reveal possible locations of the display. In the photo of the coffee sign in Figure 2, there is a local aspect due to the handwriting, but without knowing the photo was taken in Germany, the display itself does not offer any clues regarding its location, creating a similar de-nationalized effect. In Figure 2, the only hints come from aspects of its placement, such as the European-style tiles of the sidewalk seen behind the sign in the photo. The same is true for the licorice ad in Figure 4 and the particular frame captured by the photo of the burger restaurant in Figure 3.

In Figure 5, we can see another example of de-nationalized English that indexes wellness.

Figure 5. De-nationalized English indexing wellness in Mannheim

The display in Figure 5 is attached to a light post. It is a metal sign, with white and pink printing on a black background. The business name is “Work Sleep Boardinghouse.” At the top of the display “work sleep” is written in pink, and in between the words a white stylized blossom like a lotus flower. Below that, in white, “boardinghouse” is written in a different font and smaller text size. In the middle, the text reads “No.1 für Handwerker | Monteure | Geschäftsreisende” (‘No 1 for tradesmen | technicians | business travellers’), again in white, yet another font, and smaller text size. On the right side, there is a QR code. At the bottom, four pink arrows point in the direction of the place. In the middle of this line of arrows, the distance to the business is written in white as “450m.” The display directions span geographical space from the display’s immediate location in close proximity, and therefore deictically anchored (Stroud & Mpendukana, 2009: 369), to a virtual space via the QR code (see Blommaert 2013). The display is above eye level at a height of about 2-3m. On the one hand, this makes it easier for people in cars to see than pedestrians, on the other, the sign is relatively small and the QR code can only be used by pedestrians. Pedestrians would indicate primarily an audience that is more likely local, whereas people in cars may be coming from further away.

The colour scheme, the stylized lotus flower, and the rounded font are reminiscent of Asian-style spas and connect perceived Southeast Asian aesthetics to the local context. Because of the close association between Southeast Asia and spas, these design elements also convey the kind of escape associated with relaxation and wellness. The choice of English for the name also supports this. However, this creates an immediate discongruence, as the immediate and explicit use of “work” is at odds with relaxation and wellness and sends mixed messages. The use of English leads to mixed messages as well. While the visual and linguistic elements seem to be used to create an elevated image aimed at white collar luxury spa experience, the target audience is explicitly referenced on the display: “Handwerker” means tradesmen or craftsmen, “Monteure” are technicians, likewise in the sense of vocational school-educated people.

Both German words are used in their masculine form. While this might indicate that the establishment expects primarily male guests from fields of work that are male-dominated, the generic masculine—that is, using the grammatically masculine form to refer to both men and women—used to be widely accepted in German but has been criticized since at least the 1970s (e.g., Pusch, 1984), followed by waves of pushes for gender-neutral language use and backlashes. In the present, primarily conservative and right-wing groups are known to demonstratively reject gender-neutral language in favour of the generic masculine forms. While of course not firmly determining factors, right-wing and conservative views tend to be associated with lower levels of formal education and corresponding socioeconomic class. The use of professions listed as target audience therefore matches the use of a generic reading of the grammatically masculine forms. Interestingly, “Geschäftsreisende”, meaning business travellers, is a gender-neutral form and could refer to white collar work. It uses the German participle form and, in fact, does not have a specifically feminine or masculine plural form.

In summary, as in Figures 2 and 4, a membership category relating to class is constructed through the rescaling here: design and language choice referencing Southeast Asian aesthetics indicate the distance that make first-hand experiences likely financially

unobtainable for socioeconomic classes with insufficient disposable income or leisure time for long-distance travel. As this distance limits accessibility, it heightens the status of the location or product. In the local context, such references typically justify a higher price by attaching the connotation of the inaccessible to a local or imported product. The wellness industry as a whole typically targets the middle class and above in their marketing. However, the explicitly mentioned target groups are predominantly working class, and the grammatical forms referencing them, intentionally or not, adhere to that class’s perceived linguistic preferences. This incongruence could be unintentional and attributed to non-professional designers, but the design and language choices could also be read as aspirational and elevating: Like luxury items, this could allow working class travellers to signal a higher social standing.

Conclusion

The above analysis shows different ways that English can be commodified by combining with other elements of a commercial semiotic display to construct membership categories and commodified rescaling effects. Membership categories are used strategically by businesses to create identities for their possible customers in two German cities, and it is through these strategic uses of English that they convey who they want their products to appeal to and invite would-be customers to step into these constructed identity-worlds. In Figure 1, English taken from an American pop culture reference is used on a commercial sign for a bakery to generate a specifically local, even iconically local, meaning. The recognizability of the English-language reference and the other related parts of the semiotic display (such as particular fonts) are crucial elements without which the local meaning could not be generated. In Figure 2, English is used in a free and original way on a commercial sign for a coffee shop to align with international coffee culture and food lifestyles. Here, English serves to construct youthful and middle-class membership categories associated with busy and cosmopolitan students, thereby contrasting their customers with those who frequent traditional European cafés associated with older and upper-middle-class clientele.

In Figure 3, English is used as an emblem of American identity and culture in signage within a US fast food chain restaurant. This contrasts with the previous two examples in which English is used to construct specifically local membership categories, whereas here it instead erases the local and creates a specifically American membership category, but nonetheless one which locals can be included within. Combined with layout and design elements, English is used in Figure 4 on a commercial sign for a Danish candy to construct a membership category that again relates to class. However, unlike the youthful and middle-class category constructed in Figure 2, here we instead see English used to construct a category of luxury and affluence. The de-nationalized nature of the membership category constructed here also contrasts with the specifically American membership category constructed in Figure 3. Finally, in Figure 5, layout and design elements combine with English to construct a membership category for would-be working-class clientele of a boarding house, but one that aspires to an elevated, luxurious experience, conveyed through the commercial sign’s subtle references to the escape of South Asian aesthetics and wellness culture.

Each of the customer identities constructed through membership categorization in these examples of commodified English relates to age and/or class. However, the sheer breadth of these age-related and class-related identities is striking. We have shown that the use of English in a commercial context in Germany does not automatically imply only one specific age or class that is always automatically associated with English, but a whole array of them. From the perspective of a potential customer, this means that arriving at the intended interpretation of the English on an individual commercial sign is highly dependent on other elements, such as register and design, and on both international and local cultural elements. Relatedly, our analysis also shows that while it is indeed the case that the use of English can be used to convey modernity and internationality (as would be expected based on previous research on the commodification of English in the SL both in Germany and elsewhere), it notably is also used to construct specifically local customer identities in a way that depends not just on the global connotations of English but also on elements of the local culture. The fact that English can represent so many different things to vastly different clienteles suggests that, in terms of Graeber's (2001) categories of value, English is seen as valuable in an economic or sociological sense not just to the particular groups of people normally associated with English use in Germany (such as young or educated people or tourists). Instead, English can be used to appeal to anyone who aspires to feel like they could be a part of those groups, even if only for the short amount of time it takes to stay in a boarding house, eat a burger, or drink a coffee. In serving this kind of function, then, commodified English becomes not just about using a global language to index specific connotations of modernity and internationality that it is always automatically associated with, but a way of communicating what is desirable that relies on all of the specifically local (rescaled) connotations of English as a global language, a deep knowledge of the audience for each sign, and an anticipation of what different groups of people might want.

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